

Emergency Department Performance Parameters and Process Flow in a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital**T. K. Jayakumar¹, Saritha J Shenoy², Ronnie Thomas³, Sujatha V N⁴, Arun Aravindhan V⁵**¹Professor, Department of Cardiovascular and Thoracic surgery, Govt. Medical College, Kottayam, Kerala²Associate Professor, Department of Physiology, Govt. Medical College, Kottayam, Kerala³Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Govt. Medical College, Kottayam, Kerala⁴Research Assistant, Department of Cardiovascular and Thoracic surgery, Govt. Medical College, Kottayam, Kerala⁵Engineer F, Bio Medical Technology wing, Sree Chitra Institute of Medical Sciences, Thiruvananthapuram

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Abstract:**Background:** The emergency department (ED) provides immediate care to patients, and identifying the challenges and understanding the process flow helps establish an efficient ED, for improving outcomes and meeting standards. This study aims to analyze the ED patient population, quantify wait times, and map the process flow.**Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted on 349 willing patients selected from consecutive sampling, across all time frames. Demographic details, presenting complaints, wait times and process flow were manually collected using Epicollect software version 5.1 & analysed using Jamovi and R software.**Results:** Among 349 patients, 238 were males and 111 were females, majority were 41 -60 years . 48%medical, 21% surgical and 29% trauma cases were reported. 83% were below poverty line & 32.95% were unemployed, 20.3% unskilled laborers & rest were homemakers, skilled laborers, students. Median waiting times for triage and initial physician assessment in medical, surgical, and trauma emergencies were 4, 3, and 3.5 minutes, and 1, 1.2, and 1 minute, respectively. Wait times for initial lab tests were 24, 253, and 121 minutes, respectively. Reassessment by a doctor and CT scan wait times were 129, 194.5, 115 minutes, and 35, 108, 84.5 minutes, respectively.**Conclusion:** Among 349 patients, the majority were unemployed males 41-60 age, 83% below the poverty line. 48% medical, 21% surgical and 29% trauma cases . While triage and initial physician assessment wait times were satisfactory, they were prolonged for lab tests, radiological investigations, and reassessment.**Keywords:** Emergency Department Performance, Process Flow, Waits Times.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

An emergency is an unforeseen state in which normal procedures are suspended and extraordinary measures are taken in order to prevent a disaster. The performance and efficiency of an ED directly impacts patient outcomes and satisfaction [1]. The daily fluctuations in routine critical care provide a foundation of preparedness for the less-frequent, larger events that affect most health care organizations at some time. Although large disasters can overburden the ED, those who strengthen processes through daily practice will be the best prepared to manage them [2]. Due to an increasing number of mass casualty incidents, which are generally complex and unique in nature,

operational research methodologies aid in planning emergency services enhance quality of care and survival rate of patients. This includes improving a wide range of processes involving patient flow from the initial call to the ED through disposition, discharge home, or admission to the hospital [3]. ED activities occurring during the front-end processing of patients can vary from one ED to another; however, they typically include initial patient presentation, registration, triage, bed placement, and medical evaluation. When these processes do not occur simultaneously or in immediate succession, a patient is typically required to wait in a queue. The time needed to

complete these front-end processes contributes to the ED total length of stay [4]. Many researchers undertook studies to determine the average waiting time of patients coming into the emergency department and to assess the factors responsible for the waiting period of patients in the emergency department [5]. The aim of this study is to map the process flow and quantify the waiting time of patients at ED in order to identify the bottle necks and flaws in patient flow so that remedial measures can be planned and better critical care can be provided. Each institution will have its own problems and identification of the bottle necks will help to improve ED. Identification & immediate interventions will add to the overall knowledge in setting up/modifying any ED.

The objectives of the present study is to estimate the waiting time of patients at various locations, describe the patient category in the ED, identify the bottle neck & flaws in patient flow and map the process flow of patients at emergency department.

Materials & Methods

This was a cross-sectional descriptive study using quantitative methods for analysis. It was conducted at the emergency department of GMCH, Kottayam. All patients were selected through a consecutive sampling process. Ethical approvals were taken and ED staff was briefed on the processes and all the documentation of the project. After taking informed consent, demographic details of patients reporting to ED were collected and they were categorized based on presenting complaints. The patients were selected in all time frames at ED.

The 24hrs in a day was divided into four slots – 8 am to 2pm, 2pm to 8pm, 8pm to 2am and 2am to 8am and uniform selection of patients was done from each slot. The selected patients were categorized → Trauma, Medical, Surgical, & Exacerbation of pre-existing conditions.

The detailed methodology is as follows

(a) To quantify the waiting time of patients at various locations & identify flaws in patient flow- Four time-based elements was identified which was assessed using process mapping

- Patient entering into the system
- Lab including radiology
- Therapeutic decision and intervention

- Patient moving out of the system after intervention

A Performa was prepared to record –

- The demographic details,
- Arrival to departure time from ED of admitted patients & discharged patients,
- Initial time of assessment by nurse,
- Initial time of assessment by doctor,
- Arrival to departure time at consulted specialty
- Time of laboratory investigation,
- Time of radiological investigation

The progress and time in and out of each patient passing through each area and process was recorded using time logs.

(b) Mapping the process flow of patients- was carefully done by direct observation and coding the specific points. The category and demographic details of patients reporting to the ED were identified. The process map was done using Epicollect version 5.1 software.

Inclusion Criteria: All patients, bystanders and other health care workers who are willing and stakeholders of this study

Sample Size

$$n = \frac{Z\alpha^2 \times SD^2}{L^2} = \frac{3.84 \times 1.26^2}{\left(\frac{10}{100} \times 2.46\right)^2}$$

$$Z\alpha^2 = 3.84, SD = 1.26, L = 10\% \text{ of } 2.46 (5)$$

102 patients will be selected in each category - Trauma, Medical & Surgical.

(Sreekala P, Arpita Dan, Elizabeth M Varghese Patient Waiting Time in Emergency Department International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 5, Issue 5, May 2015 1 ISSN 2250-3153)[11].

Sampling Technique: Systematic Random sampling with matrix, Sampling frame – casualty register.

Data Collection Tools: Electronic data capture using Epicollect 5.

Data Management and Analysis: Data will be analysed using Jamovi & R software (free).

Results

Figure 1: Age & Gender distribution of ED patients

A total of 349 patients were included in the study in which 238 were males and 111 females. Among the total patients studied 12.89% were in below 18 years, 21.48% were in 19 to 40 years, 32.6% were in 41 to 60 years, 28.3% were in 61 to 80 years and 0.04% was above 80 years.

Figure 2: Age groups and ED Patient category

168 medical emergencies (48%), 75 surgical emergencies (21%), 104 were trauma cases (29%) and 2 cases were exacerbation of pre-existing conditions.

Figure 3: Socio-economic Status & ED Patient category

83% patients were in below poverty line category and 17% were in above poverty line category.

Figure 4: Occupation & ED Patient category

0.02% government employees/ professionals/ business, 12% homemakers, 0.02% Shop owner/Clerical jobs, 12.6% skilled labourer, 16.3% students, 32.95% unemployed & 20.3% unskilled labourer.

Among the various categories of occupation - 40% of government employees/professional/business patients were in medical emergencies, 30% each in surgical & trauma. 40% of homemaker patients were in medical emergencies, 23% in surgical & 35% were trauma. Among shop owner/Clerical

jobs patients, 57% were in medical emergencies, 14% in surgical & 28% trauma. 43% of skilled labourer patients were in medical emergencies, 18% in surgical & 38% trauma.

29.8% of students as patients were in medical emergencies, 19.2% in surgical & 50.8% trauma. 68.6% of patients who were unemployed were in medical emergencies, 20.8% in surgical & 10.4% trauma. 39.4% of unskilled labourer patients were in medical emergencies, 23.9% in surgical & 36.6% trauma.

Table 1: Level of severity & ED Patient category

ED patient category	Green	Red	Yellow
Medical emergency	68	56	44
Surgical emergency	51	4	20
Trauma/RTA/Domestic accident	76	5	23

Among the medical emergency patients, 33.33% were admitted to red zone 40.4% to the green zone & 26% to the yellow zone. Among the Surgical emergency patients 5.33% were admitted to the red zone, 68% to the green zone & 26.6% to yellow zone. Among the trauma patients 4.8% were admitted to red zone 73.07% to green zone & 22.1% to yellow zone.

Table 2: Distribution of Patient wait times according to ED category

Description of wait time (minutes)		Medical Emergency (minutes)	Surgical Emergency (minutes)	Trauma / RTA / Domestic accident	Exacerbation of pre-existing condition (minutes)	p value
1. Waiting time for Triage	Mean ± SD	5.04 ± 11.45	4.79 ± 3.72	10.75 ± 58.15	351.0 ± 482.25	<0.001
	Median (IQR)	4	3	3.5	341	
2. Initial physician assessment wait time	Mean ± SD	4.04 ± 16.4	5.49 ± 13.4	1.82 ± 59.5	323.5 ± 543.75	<0.001
	Median (IQR)	1	1.2	1	360	0.004
3. Waiting time for Laboratory tests	Mean ± SD	57.03 ± 132.2	42.9 ± 41.2	240.8 ± 365.6	NA	0.001
	Median (IQR)	24	25	121	NA	0.0001
4. Waiting time for reassessment by physician	Mean ± SD	166.9 ± 218.9	253.4 ± 228.6	249.3 ± 364.9	NA	0.09
	Median (IQR)	129	194.5	115		0.002
5. Waiting time for CT scan after receipt of CT request	Mean ± SD	98.04 ± 257.5	166.8 ± 301.9	256.8 ± 461.9	N/A	0.03
	Median (IQR)	35	108	84.5	N/A	

A p- value of < 0.05 is statistically significant and < 0.001 is highly significant

The median waiting time for triage in medical, surgical & trauma emergencies was 4, 3 & 3.5 minutes respectively. The initial physician assessment wait time in medical, surgical & trauma emergencies was 1, 1.2 & 1 minute respectively. The waiting time for initial Lab tests in medical, surgical & trauma emergencies was 24, 25 & 121 minutes respectively.

The wait time for reassessment by doctor in medical, surgical & trauma emergencies was 129, 194.5 & 115 minutes respectively. The waiting time for CT scan after receipt of CT request in medical, surgical & trauma emergencies was 35, 108 & 84.5 minutes respectively.

Table 3: Distribution of Patient wait times according to severity score

Description of wait time (minutes)		Severity Score-Red (minutes)	Severity Score-Yellow (minutes)	Severity Score-Green (minutes)	p value
1. Waiting time for TRIAGE	Mean ± SD	5.01 ± 9.3	6.32 ± 14.9	4.03 ± 66.3	0.94
	Median (IQR)	3	5	4	
2. Initial physician assessment wait time	Mean ± SD	1.9 ± 4.6	5.1 ± 14.6	13.7 ± 67.8	0.198
	Median (IQR)	1	1.1	1.5	
3. Waiting time for Laboratory tests	Mean ± SD	46.5 ± 126.9	126.4 ± 256.8	61.5 ± 161.5	0.129
	Median (IQR)	18	58	26	0.0003
4. Waiting time for reassessment by physician	Mean ± SD	198.4 ± 239.6	241.5 ± 281.9	209.4 ± 268.8	0.715
	Median (IQR)	85	157	145	0.01

A p- value of < 0.05 is statistically significant and < 0.001 is highly significant

The median waiting time for triage in Red, yellow & Green zones was 3, 5 & 4 minutes respectively. The initial physician assessment wait time in Red, yellow & Green zone was 1, 1.1 & 1.5 minutes

respectively. The waiting time for initial Lab tests in Red, yellow & Green zone was 18, 58 & 26 minutes respectively.

The wait time for reassessment by a doctor in Red, yellow & Green zone was 85, 157 & 145 minutes respectively.

Process flow mapping

Figure 5:

Discussion

The study aimed to map the process flow and quantify the waiting times of patients in the ED of a tertiary care teaching hospital, revealing significant insights into patient demographics, the nature of emergencies, and bottlenecks in patient care. The study included 349 patients, with a male predominance (68.2%) and a significant portion (32.6%) in the 41-60 age groups.

Most patients (83%) were below the poverty line, indicating socioeconomic factors heavily influence ED visits. Medical emergencies constituted the majority (48%), followed by trauma (29%) and surgical emergencies (21%). The median waiting time for triage was 4 minutes for medical, 3 minutes for surgical and 3.5 minutes for trauma emergency. Initial physician assessment times were 1 minute for medical, 1.2 minutes for surgical and 1 minute for trauma. These times indicate efficient initial handling, aligning with studies suggesting

optimal triage can significantly enhance ED efficiency [12]. The waiting times for lab tests were significantly longer: 24 minutes for medical, 25 minutes for surgical and 121 minutes for trauma emergencies. Reassessment by physicians also showed prolonged waiting times: 129 minutes for medical, 194.5 minutes for surgical and 115 minutes for trauma. Prolonged diagnostic and reassessment times are critical bottlenecks, corroborating previous findings that delays in these areas significantly impact overall ED performance [13]. The waiting time for CT scans was long, with medians of 35 minutes for medical, 108 minutes for surgical, and 84.5 minutes for trauma emergency. These delays reflect a need for more efficient imaging processes, which have been highlighted as crucial for improving ED throughput and patient outcomes.

Conclusion

The data reveals critical areas for improvement in ED operations and streamlining diagnostic processes. The high percentage of patients below the poverty line suggests a need for targeted interventions to address socioeconomic barriers affecting ED use and outcomes. By addressing diagnostic and reassessment delays, the hospital can enhance its emergency care services, ultimately leading to better health outcomes and patient satisfaction.

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